

Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH) Assay Kit

(Colorimetric Method)

Serial No: A020-1

Pack: 50T/24S
100T/48S

Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institute

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1. INTRODUCTION

This kit applies to measure lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity in animal serum, tissues, perfusate, cell culture fluid, etc.

This kit can be used for laboratory research only.

(1) Assay significance:

Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) exists in human body tissues and organs. LDH is an important enzyme in energy metabolism of organism, changes of quality and amount of LDH will affect energy metabolism of organism. When tissues or organs have pathological changes, their LDH will change also, and can cause LDH changes in blood.

LDH increasing mainly appears in acute myocardial infarction, virus hepatitis, cirrhosis of liver, pulmonary infarction, some malignant tumors, skeletal muscles disease, nucleated erythrocyte inner marrow histoclasia (invalid hematogenesis), leukemia, especially acute lymphocytic leukemia, malignant anaemia.

In acute myocardial infarction, LDH level starts to increase at 12-24 hours after attack, peak time is at 48-72 hours, LDH increasing can last for 10 days. LDH increasing appears when malignant tumors develop to certain stage, so it has low significance for tumor early diagnosis. In hydrothorax or hydroperitoneum caused by some types of tumor, LDH activity always increases.

In addition, LDH total activity increasing in cerebrospinal fluid appears when subarachnoid hemorrhage happens or cerebral vessels have thrombopoiesis and hemorrhage. Brain neoplasms and meningeal neoplasms do not cause LDH total activity increasing, but neoplasm metastasis from other positions will cause.

LDH activity can increase to 3-6 times of normal level in urine from patients of chronic glomerulonephritis, systemic lupus erythematosus, diabetic nephrosclerosis, malignant tumor in bladder or kidney. But urea or small molecular peptides can restrain LDH activity, low pH in urine may cause LDH inactivation also.

Chronic nephrotic patients with uremia have normal blood serum LDH generally, but LDH activity will increase after dialysis treatment, it phenomenon may relate to LDH inhibitors in serum such as urea and oxalate are removed during dialysis.

(2) Assay principle:

Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) can catalyze lactic acid to pyruvic acid, pyruvic acid reacts with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine to produce pyruvic dinitrophenylhydrazone. The product appears red-brown in alkaline solution, enzyme activity can be worked out by measuring absorbances.

2. REAGENT COMPOSITION & PREPARATION (50T/48S)

This kit can be stored at 2~8°C hermetically, up to 3 months.

Composition (R is abbreviation of reagent)		Pack	
		100T/48S	50T/24S
R1	Matrix buffer, stored at 2~8°C	30ml×1 bottle	15ml×1 bottle
R2	Coenzyme I, stored at -20°C	Powder×3 vials	Powder×2 vials
<p>Coenzyme I solution preparation: Add 1.3ml distilled water in each vial of powder, after dissolving, store tubes at freezing temperature for 2 weeks, if you want to use this solution several times, it is suggested to subpackage before freeze(avoid freeze-thawing repeatedly)</p>			
R3	2,4-dinitro-phenylhydrazine, stored at 2~8°C	30ml×1 bottle	15ml×1 bottle
R4	4mol/L NaOH solution, stored at 2~8°C.	30ml×1 bottle	15ml×1 bottle
<p>0.4mol/L NaOH solution preparation: Dilute 4mol/L NaOH 10 times with distilled water, how much you use, how much you make.</p>			
R5	2mmol/L sodium pyruvate standard solution, stored at 2~8°C	1ml×1 vial	1ml×1 vial

3. REQUIRED EQUIPMENTS & REAGENTS

- An spectrophotometer capable of measuring absorbance at 440nm
- Thermostatic water bath or air bath capable of controlling temperature at 37°C
- Desk centrifuge
- Micropipets and tips
- Vortex mixer
- A source of pure water (preferably double distilled water and double distilled water)

4. OPERATION PROCEDURE

	Blank well B(ml)	Standard well S(ml)	Sample well U(ml)	Contrast well C(ml)
Distilled water	0.05+a	0.05		0.05
2mmol/L standard solution		a		
Sample to assay			a	a
Matrix buffer	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Coenzyme I			0.05	
Mix sufficiently, place in 37°C water bath for 15 minutes				
2,4--dinitrophenylhydrazine	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Mix sufficiently, place in 37°C water bath for 15 minutes				

0.4mol/L NaOH solution	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Mix sufficiently, place at room temperature for 3 minutes, measure all tubes' absorbances at 440nm in cuvette of 1cm light path (use distilled water to adjust zero).				

***Referenced sampling volume:** take 10~50μl 0.2% mouse brain tissue homogenate, take 10~30μl rat blood serum. If LDH activity in sample have too high, you can dilute sample with physiological saline before assay. Probing method details can be found in appendix.

Note: 1. Do not add coenzyme I in blank tube.

2. All operations should according to this manual, never add coenzyme I before add matrix buffer solution.

5. CALCULATION

(1) Blood serum (or plasma) LDH assay:

Definition: 1000ml blood serum(or plasma) reacts with matrix at 37°C for 15 minutes and produces 1 μ mol pyruvic acid in reaction system, it is considered as 1 Unit.

Formula:

$$\text{Blood serum (or plasma) LDH activity (U/L)} = \frac{OD_U - OD_C}{OD_S - OD_B} \times C_S \times N \times 1000$$

(2) Tissue LDH assay:

Definition: 1g tissue protein reacts with matrix at 37°C for 15 minutes and produces 1 μ mol pyruvic acid in reaction system, it is 1 Unit.

Formula:

$$\text{Tissue LDH activity (U/gprot)} = \frac{OD_U - OD_C}{OD_S - OD_B} \times C_S \div C_{\text{prot}}$$

In formulas:

OD_U—Absorbance of sample tube

OD_B—Absorbance of blank tube

OD_S—Absorbance of standard tube

OD_C—Absorbance of contrast tube

C_S—Standard concentration (2mmol/L)

N—Sample dilute multiple before assay

C_{prot}—Protein concentration in sample to assay (gprot/ml)

(3) Examples:

① Example for blood serum (or plasma) calculation:

Take 0.02 ml rat blood serum to measure LDH activity, in results, OD_U is 0.313, OD_C is 0.099, OD_S is 0.298, OD_B is 0.075.

$$\text{Blood serum (or plasma) LDH activity (U/L)} = \frac{0.313 - 0.099}{0.298 - 0.075} \times 2 \times 1000 \times 1 = 1919.28 \text{ U/L}$$

① Examples for tissue calculation:

a. Take 0.015ml 1% rat lung tissue homogenate to assay LDH activity, in results, OD_U is 0.485, OD_C is 0.069, OD_S is 0.240, OD_B is 0.070, protein concentration in 1% homogenate is 0.635mg/ml (0.635 × 10⁻³g/ml).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tissue LDH activity (U/gprot)} &= \frac{0.485 - 0.069}{0.240 - 0.070} \times 2 \div (0.635 \times 10^{-3}) \\ &= 7707.27 \text{ U/gprot} \end{aligned}$$

b. Take 0.02ml 0.2% mouse brain tissue homogenate to assay LDH activity, in results, OD_U is 0.472, OD_C is 0.264, OD_S is 0.298, OD_B is 0.075, protein concentration in 2% homogenate is 0.850mg/ml (0.850 × 10⁻³g/ml).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tissue LDH activity (U/gprot)} &= \frac{0.472 - 0.264}{0.298 - 0.075} \times 2 \div (0.850 \times 10^{-4}) \\ &= 21946.72 \text{ U/gprot} \end{aligned}$$

6. ABOUT COMPANY

Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institute Nanjing Jiancheng Technology Co.Ltd.

Address:	Room 1106, Floor 11, New Li-Ji Mansion, No.258-27, Zhongyang Road, Nanjing	Teleph one:	(025) 83360321 83360969 83113890
Postcode:	210009		83112287(finance s) 83360272(technol ogy)
Contanct person:	Jianping Ji	Fax:	(025) 83227943 83609960
Complaint phone:	(025) 57713719/13813881385	Messag e:	13815858329
Homepage:	www.njcbio.com (Jiancheng biology) www.njctech.com (Jiancheng technology)	E-mail:	njcbio@vip.163.com answer@njcbio.com

APPENDIX I: Use ROCHE company's LDH standard to draw standard curve

7.5U/ml LDH standard preparation: Take 10 μ l LDH standard (its activity at 37 $^{\circ}$ C is 7500U/ml), dilute until its volume reaches to 10ml.

Tube No.	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
7.5U/ml LDH standard (ml)	0	0.005	0.010	0.015	0.020	0.025	0.030	0.035	0.040
Distilled water (ml)	0.04	0.035	0.030	0.025	0.020	0.015	0.010	0.005	0
Matrix buffer (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Mix sufficiently, place in 37 $^{\circ}$ C water bath for 15 minutes.									
2,4- dinitro-phenylhydrazine solution (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Mix sufficiently, place in 37 $^{\circ}$ C water bath for 15 minutes.									
0.4mol/L NaOH solution (ml)	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Mix sufficiently, place quiescently for 3 minutes, measure all tubes' absorbances at 440nm in cuvettes of 1cm light path (use distilled water to adjust zero).									
Corresponding LDH unit	0	595	2010	3027	3870	4443	4886	5146	5276
Referenced absorbances from our Institute	0.215	0.270	0.396	0.500	0.573	0.626	0.667	0.691	0.703
Referenced absolute absorbances from our Institute	0	0.055	0.182	0.285	0.358	0.411	0.452	0.476	0.488

Use measured OD values as y-axis, use corresponding LDH activity units as x-axis, draw standard curve.

APPENDIX II: Rat blood plasma LDH sampling volume probing

1. Reagents and preparations: Reagents are offered by 1st substation of Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institute, preparations are based on this manual.

2. Sample source: Rat whole blood (normal group, take blood from eye sockets) and blood plasma (use heparin for anticoagulation) from Nanjing Medical College.

3. Operator : Jiancheng detection department

4. Date: 2005-11-15

5. Operation table:

	Standard tube	Blank tube	Sample tube	Contrast tube
Distilled water (ml)	0.13	0.15		0.05
Standard (ml)	0.02			
Samples of different concentrations (ml)			0.10	0.10
Matrix buffer (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Coenzyme I (ml)			0.05	
Mix sufficiently, place in 37°C water bath for 15 minutes.				
2,4- dinitro-phenylhydrazine solution (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Mix sufficiently, place in 37°C water bath for 15 minutes.				
0.4mol/L NaOH solution (ml)	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Mix sufficiently, place at room temperature for 3 minutes, measure all tubes' absorbances at 440nm in cuvettes of 1cm light path (adjust zero by distilled water).				

6. Result:

Tube No.	0	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	Sample 6	Sample 7
Plasma (ml)	0	0.005	0.010	0.020	0.040	0.060	0.080	0.100
Double distilled water (ml)	0.1	0.095	0.090	0.080	0.060	0.040	0.020	0
OD value of sample tube	0.232	0.321	0.390	0.510	0.690	0.796	0.900	0.968
OD value of contrast tube	0.232	0.260	0.275	0.316	0.391	0.470	0.556	0.611
Absolute OD value	0	0.061	0.115	0.194	0.299	0.326	0.344	0.357

7. Optimal sampling volume probing curve of rat blood plasma LDH assay (37°C water bath)

Referenced sampling volume: Take 10~30 μl rat plasma, optimal sampling volume is 20 μl . The enzyme curve is treated by regression curve in this range, appears direct proportion relatively. If sampling volume is too high or too low, then there will be no significant deviations during statistical treatment after experiment.

APPENDIX III: 0.2% mouse brain tissue homogenate LDH sampling volume probing

1. Reagents and preparations: Reagents are offered by 1st substation of Nanjing Jiancheng Bioengineering Institute, preparations are based on this manual.

2. Sample source: Normal mouse brain tissue (already stored at -30°C for 2 months) from Nanjing Medical College, take tissue sample and make 10% homogenate with physiological saline (details according to experimental methodology). Centrifuge at 3500rpm for 10 minutes, take 0.1ml supernatant and dilute with physiological saline to 5ml (dilute to 0.2% homogenate to assay), measured protein concentration in 2% homogenate is 0.850mgprot/ml (use Coomassie brilliant blue method to measure protein concentration).

3. Operator : Jiancheng detection department

4. Date: 2005-11-15

5. Operation table:

	Standard tube	Blank tube	Sample tube	Contrast tube
Distilled water (ml)	0.13	0.15		0.05
Standard (ml)	0.02			
Samples of different concentrations (ml)			0.10	0.10
Matrix buffer (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Coenzyme I solution (ml)			0.05	
Mix sufficiently, place in 37°C water bath for 15 minutes.				

2,4-dinitro-phenylhydrazine solution (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Mix sufficiently, place in 37°C water bath for 15 minutes.				
0.4mol/L NaOH solution (ml)	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Mix sufficiently, place at room temperature for 3 minutes, measure all tubes' absorbances at 440nm in cuvettes of 1cm light path (use distilled water to adjust zero).				

6. Result:

Tube No.	0	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4	Sample 5	Sample 6	Sample 7
0.2% homogenate (ml)	0	0.005	0.010	0.020	0.040	0.060	0.080	0.100
Double distilled water (ml)	0.1	0.095	0.090	0.080	0.060	0.040	0.020	0
Sample OD value	0.232	0.323	0.386	0.472	0.574	0.648	0.688	0.724
Contrast OD value	0.232	0.250	0.261	0.264	0.267	0.270	0.272	0.280
Absolute OD value	0	0.073	0.125	0.208	0.307	0.378	0.416	0.444

7. Optimal sampling volume probing curve of mouse brain homogenate LDH assay: (37°C water bath)

0.2% mouse brain homogenate sampling volume (μl)

Referenced sampling volume: Take 20~50 μl 0.2% mouse brain homogenate, optimal sampling volume is 35~40 μl. The enzyme curve is treated by regression curve in this range, appears direct proportion relatively. If sampling volume is too high or too low, then there will be no significant deviations during statistical treatment after experiment.